

The background of the cover is a composite image. On the left, there is an aerial photograph of a river winding through a dry, brown landscape. On the right, there is a dark blue background with a white line graph showing fluctuating data points, overlaid with a faint grid pattern.

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES TO
WATER RESOURCE
MANAGEMENT IN
ARID REGIONS IN THE
CONTEXT OF
CLIMATE CHANGE**

PROCEEDINGS
(Conference Proceedings)

May 19, 2026

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

WICAR-2026

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International Scientific and Practical Conference -2026

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO WATER RESOURCE MANAGEMENT IN ARID REGIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CLIMATE CHANGE

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference innovative approaches to water resource management in arid regions in the context of climate change on May 19, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The conference aims to discuss key issues of effective water resource management in arid regions under climate change, develop and apply innovative approaches and mathematical and computational modeling methods, share recent research results and practical experience, and strengthen international academic cooperation in this field.

Key Themes of the Conference:

1. Water Diplomacy and Integrated Approaches in International Relation: Interdisciplinary Approaches to Sustainable Development, Communication and Global Security

- Issues of systemic analysis in international relations and world politics in the context of water diplomacy
- Economic, environmental and energy aspects of sustainable development
- Systemic approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

2. Mathematical and computer modeling of optimal water resources management under climate change

- Optimal water resource management under climate change
- Modeling water resource dynamics and climate variability
- Methods of applied and computational mathematics in irrigation system modeling.

3. Environmental and Hydrogeological Processes in the Aral Sea Region: Analysis Based on Modern Technologies

- Analysis of hydrogeological processes in the Aral Sea region
- Application of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and big data technologies to environmental challenges
- Simulation and stochastic modeling of environmental and hydrogeological processes in the Aral region.

The event was conducted in a hybrid format with participation in English, Russian, and Uzbek. The conference provided a high-level platform for scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dinamik sistemalarning boshlang'ich tushunchalari (Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teorema va uning misollardagi tahlillari).

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Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teorema.

Qo'zg'almas nuqta deb $F(x_0) = x_0$ shartini qanoatlantiradigan x_0 nuqtaga aytiladi. E'tibor bering, $F^2(x_0) = F(F(x_0)) = F(x_0) = x_0$ va umuman olganda, $F^n(x_0) = x_0$. Shunday qilib, qo'zg'almas nuqtaning orbitasi x_0, x_0, x_0, \dots ko'rinishidagi o'zgarmas ketma-ketlikdan iborat. [3, 4]

Yuqorida [3, 4] maqolada qo'zg'almas nuqta va uni topish haqida fikr yuritgan edik. Endilikda ushbu maqolada biz qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni topish va nuqtaning xususiyatlarini o'rganib chiqishga harakat qilamiz. Qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni topishning eng oddiy mezonlaridan biri matematik analizning quyidagi muhim faktidan kelib chiqadi:

Oraliq qiymat haqidagi teorema (The Intermediate Value Theorem). Faraz qilaylik, $F: [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ funksiya uzluksiz bo'lsin. y_0 qiymati $F(a)$ va $F(b)$ orasida yotsin. U holda $[a, b]$ intervalida shunday x_0 nuqta mavjudki, unda $F(x_0) = y_0$ bo'ladi.

Soddaroq aytganda, bu teorema bizga uzluksiz funksiya $[a, b]$ intervalida $F(a)$ va $F(b)$ orasidagi barcha qiymatlarni qabul qilishini aytadi. Buning bevosita natijasi quyidagicha:

Qo'zg'almas nuqta haqidagi teorema (Fixed Point Theorem). Faraz qilaylik, $F: [a, b] \rightarrow [a, b]$ funksiya uzluksiz bo'lsin. U holda $[a, b]$ oraliqda F uchun kamida bitta qo'zg'almas nuqta mavjud.

Jalb qilish va Itarish (Attraction and Repulsion)

Qo'zg'almas nuqtalarning bir-biridan keskin farq qiluvchi ikki turi mavjud: **jalb qiluvchi** va **itruvchi** qo'zg'almas nuqtalar.

Ta'rif. Faraz qilaylik, x_0 nuqta F funksiya uchun qo'zg'almas nuqta bo'lsin. U holda:

- Agar $|F'(x_0)| < 1$ bo'lsa, x_0 **jalb qiluvchi (attracting)** qo'zg'almas nuqta deyiladi.
- Agar $|F'(x_0)| > 1$ bo'lsa, x_0 **itruvchi (repelling)** qo'zg'almas nuqta deyiladi.
- Nihoyat, agar $|F'(x_0)| = 1$ bo'lsa, qo'zg'almas nuqta **neytral** yoki **befarq (indifferent)**

deb ataladi.

Ushbu terminologiyaning geometrik asosi grafik tahlil orqali tushuntiriladi. Quyidagi a, b-rasmdagi grafiklarni ko'rib chiqamiz. Bu funksiyalarning ikkalasi ham x_0 nuqtada qo'zg'almas nuqtaga ega va qo'zg'almas nuqtalar jalb qiluvchidir.

a rasm

b rasm

Yuqoridagi barcha tushunchalarning tahlilini quyida bir nechta misollar yordamida ko'rib chiqamiz.

Misol: Quyidagi funksiyani barcha qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni toping va ularni tortuvchi (attracting), itaruvchi (repelling) yoki neytral turlarga ajrating.

$$F(x) = x^2 - \frac{x}{2}$$

Yechish: Ushbu misolni yechish uchun eng avva oldingi [3, 4] maqolalarda tahlil qilib o'tganimiz kabi qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni topib olamiz, buning uchun $F(x_0) = x_0$ tenglama yechimini topamiz.

$$x^2 - \frac{x}{2} = x \Rightarrow x^2 - \frac{3x}{2} = 0$$

$$x \left(x - \frac{3}{2} \right) = 0 \Rightarrow x_1 = 0, x_2 = \frac{3}{2}$$

Ko'rinib turibdiki berilgan funksiyaning ikkita qo'zg'almas nuqtalari mavjud bo'lib, endi biz ushbu nuqtalarni itaruvchi yoki jalb qiluvchiligi yuqoridagi teoremdan aniqlaymiz, ya'ni berilgan funksiyadan hosila olib topilgan qo'zg'almas nuqtalardagi qiymatini hisoblaymiz.

$$F'(x) = 2x - \frac{1}{2} \Rightarrow F'(0) = -\frac{1}{2} \text{ va } F'\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) = \frac{5}{2}$$

Ko'rinib turibdiki ushbu qiymatlardan berilgan funksiyaning 1- qo'zg'almas ya'ni nol nuqtasi jalb qiluvchi va ikkinchi qo'zg'almas nuqtasi itaruvchi ekan.

Misol: Berilgan $F(x) = x^4 - 4x^2 + 2$ funksiyani barcha qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni toping va ularni tortuvchi (attracting), itaruvchi (repelling) yoki neytral turlarga ajrating.

Yechish: ushbu misol yechimi ham huddi yuqoridagi kabi tahlil qilinadi, shuning uchun biz quyida misol yechimini to'g'ridan-t'g'ri berib ketamiz va to'la tahlil qilmaymiz.

$$x^4 - 4x^2 + 2 = x \Rightarrow x^4 - 4x^2 - x - 2 = 0$$

$$x^2(x-2)(x+2) - (x+2) = 0$$

$$(x+2)(x^3 - 2x^2 - 1) = 0$$

Ushbu tenglamadan ko'rinadiki berilgan funksiyaning birinchi qo'zg'almas nuqtasi $x_1 = -2$ ga teng va ikkinchi. Uchunchi to'rtinchi qo'zg'almas nuqtalarini toppish uchun ma'lum bur matematik dasturlardan foydalanamiz va $x_2 = 2,2025$ ga teng bo'lgan yechim kelib chiqadi. Bundan tashqari bu berilgan funksiyaning ikkita kompleks sonlardagi yechimlari mavjud. Biz hozircha berilgan funksiyaning faqat haqiqiy qo'zg'almas nuqtalarini tekshiramiz.

$$F'(x) = 4x^3 - 8x \Rightarrow F'(-2) = -32 + 16 = -16, F'(2,2025) \approx 42,74 - 17,62 = 25,12$$

Funksiya hosilasini topilgan qo'zg'almas nuqtalardagi qiymatlariga ko'ra berilgan funksiyaning har ikkita haqiqiy qo'zg'almas nuqtalari itaruvchi ekan.

Misol: Berilgan $F(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} \sin x$ funksiyani barcha qo'zg'almas nuqtalarni toping va ularni tortuvchi (attracting), itaruvchi (repelling) yoki neytral turlarga ajrating.

Yechish: $\frac{\pi}{2} \sin x = x \Rightarrow$ ushbu tenglamaning yechimini ikki funksiya grafik tahlili orqali topish ham mumkin bo'lib,

Grafik tahlildan ko'rinib turibdiki ushbu funksiyaning 3 ta qo'zg'almas nuqtalari mavjud va ular $x_1 = -\frac{\pi}{2}$, $x_2 = 0$, $x_3 = \frac{\pi}{2}$ larga teng bo'lib, endi berilgan funksiyaning hosilasini topilgan qo'zg'almas nuqtadagi qiymatlarini tekshirib ko'ramiz.

$$F'(x) = \frac{\pi}{2} \cos x \Rightarrow F'(-\frac{\pi}{2}) = 0, F'(0) = \frac{\pi}{2} \text{ va } F'(\frac{\pi}{2}) = 0$$

Tengliklar o'rinli bo'lib yuqoridagi ta'rifga asosan berilgan funksiya $x_1 = -\frac{\pi}{2}$, $x_3 = \frac{\pi}{2}$ qo'zg'almas nuqtalari jalb qiluvchi qo'zg'almas nuqtalar va $x_2 = 0$, qo'zg'almas nuqta esa itaruvchi qo'zg'almas nuqtalar ekan.

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